

**CHEMICAL ANALYZE RESULTS OF «SPRING NO. 14», «SPRING NO. 15»
AND «SPRING NO. 16» IN GALLAOROL DISTRICT IN JIZZAKH REGION
IN UZBEKISTAN**

Tashpulatova Sabokhat Akbarovna

(PhD student)

Khodiyeva Aziza Dilshod qizi

(Bachelor degree student)

Kamiljanova Shaxrizoda Akbarovna

(Bachelor degree student)

Maxkamova Malika Axror qizi

(Bachelor degree student)

National University of Uzbekistan, Ecology Faculty, Uzbekistan

Tel: +99893 299 25 42;

E-mail: sabo_8728@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7088087>

Abstract: The spring water Spring No. 14, Spring No. 15, Spring No. 16 samples were examined by the analytical laboratory method, and the results of physical and chemical analysis of water, in particular, pH, SiO₂, dry residue, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl, NO₂, NO₃, total hardness, K, indicators such as Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al were determined. The results of chemical analysis were compared with the requirements of the national state standard for water quality and consumption.

Key words: Chemical analysis, Spring No. 14, Spring No. 15, Spring No. 16 Gallaorol district, Jizzakh region, Uzbekistan, State standards.

Springs are "a part" of underground water; their formation includes several chemical and hydrological stages and periods, and also performs a very important task (water source) in human life. In addition, the springs are considered a religious sacred destination, a beautiful place, an important object for domestic tourism. Unfortunately, in recent years, the springs are drying up and disappearing under the influence of the human factor (anthropogenic factor). Therefore, it is necessary to study and preserve them thoroughly and carefully.

These three springs, which were sampled for chemical research, are located in the villages of Gallaorol District, Jizzakh Region, Uzbekistan. This district occupies a unique mountain area and has many natural springs. Most of these springs serve as the main source of water for the population (for consumption, agriculture, livestock and other purposes).

Spring No.14, Spring No. 15, Spring No. 16 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the samples taken from

these spring water are presented and analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 14 is 7, 4, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 1.3 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 360.2 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 84.2 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 32.8 mg/dm³, Fe - 0.09 mg/dm³, and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO₃²⁻ - <5, 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 244.0, SO₄²⁻ - 61.5 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl - 14.188 (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂ - 0.01, NO₃ - 3.6 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 6.9 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 14 (Table 1).

Table 1.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 14 (mg/dm³)

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	7,1	7	Zn	0,02
2	Na	35,2	8	Ni	0,07
3	Mn	0,01	9	Co	0,30
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results (Table 1) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

Spring No.15 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the sample taken from this spring water are presented and analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 15 is 7, 1, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and

drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is neutral. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 0.8 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 295.1 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 58.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 13.4 mg/dm³, Fe - <0.05 mg/dm³ and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO₃²⁻ - <5, 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 146.4 mg/dm³, SO₄²⁻ - 80.6 mg/dm³ (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl - 14.18 mg/dm³ (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂ - 0.01 mg/dm³, NO₃ - 25.8 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 3.9 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 15 (Table 2).

Table 2.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 15 (mg/dm³)

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	2,1	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	20,8	8	Ni	0,05
3	Mn	< 0,05	9	Co	0,30
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results (Table 2) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

Spring No.16 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the sample taken from this spring water are presented and analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 16 is 7, 9, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 1.3 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The

dry residue of spring water is 320.0 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 58.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 14.6 mg/dm³, Fe - <0.05 mg/dm³ and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO₃²⁻ - <5, 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 158.6 mg/dm³, SO₄²⁻ - 105.0 mg/dm³ (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl - 14.18 mg/dm³ (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂ - 0.01 mg/dm³, NO₃ - 21.6 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 4.1 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 16 (Table 3).

Table 3.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 16 (mg/dm³)

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	2,9	7	Zn	0,02
2	Na	21,2	8	Ni	0,11
3	Mn	< 0,05	9	Co	0,38
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results (Table 3) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

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